

Maritime Data Platform for increasing data accessibility via a data space architecture

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Abstract

The amount and heterogeneity of data that needs to be managed is continuously increasing. As a result, it is becoming more and more difficult for people to find suitable data. In addition, the data is often not provided in a uniform format and is made available via a wide variety of different interfaces (e.g. via the web, in databases or CSV files). So how can a centralized and uniform search be realized that enables users to find and access suitable data despite the high degree of technical heterogeneity?

For this purpose, a Maritime Data Platform has been developed that enables unified data access to distributed data sources while considering maritime challenges such as volatile connectivity (c.f. Figure 1). In the following, the essential aspects that are in the focus of this work are described in more detail:

Data space architecture with Data Space Support Platform (DSSP) for access to distributed data sources while maintaining the sovereignty of the data providers - no physical migration of the data itself. Access to distributed data is controlled by so-called “connectors” that are connecting the data source to the platform. The connectors can be configured by the data provider so that he/she can decide which data should be exposed to which data consumer.

Handling volatile connections: Management for handling volatile connections and low bandwidth - Possibilities to tackling this are a cache for the intermediate storage of data during a connection interruption, a guarantee that messages are not only sent but have also arrived at the recipient (e.g. handshakes), and the reduction of the transmitted data volume through compression.

Monitoring of connected data sources: Continuous measurement of key figures that allow an assessment of the reliability or quality of a data source and the platform architecture itself - latency, downtime, transmission rate. If data sources show anomalies, such as excessive latency for a service or a dropped connection, a warning should also be displayed to the consumer.

Management of changing data providers: Responsibility for providing certain data (e.g., weather data) may vary from one geographic location to another. For a maritime user, however, it is (relatively) uninteresting who provides the data. The data consumers only need access to the data. If a vessel travels out of port and thereby the responsible data provider changes, the data supply should continue unchanged in the background for the data consumer (provided he has access to both data sources).

Secure authentication and authorization: Users can authenticate themselves within the platform and also authorize themselves to access the data provided for them. For this purpose, the link with the Maritime Connectivity Platform shall be established. Each user should be able to authenticate himself using his/her MCP credentials/certificate.

Encrypted communication: Since the transmitted data may be sensitive information, encrypted communication via the platform is relevant. The transmitted data must be encrypted at the connectors and forwarded to the recipient of the data. The recipient should then be able to decrypt the data again. Men-in-the-middle attacks should be made more difficult in this way.

Figure 1: Data Space Architecture for accessing heterogeneous data sources